

Acknowledgement

Phenomics Australia acknowledges First Nations people as the Traditional Custodians of the lands on which this work was imagined and realised. We pay our respects to their Elders past and present.

Thank you to our Phenomics Australia team members and host institutions for their contributions to this publication.

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Chair Report

Dr Liz Jazwinska
Board Chair,
Phenomics Australia

As Chair of the Phenomics Australia Board, I am pleased to share the exceptional achievements of our team and researchers, reflecting our dedication to advancing excellence and innovation in world-class research infrastructure.

This year, we had the opportunity to bring our team together for the Phenomics Australia Science Strategy Review. Over two days in March, our nodes, board, executives, and external panel members shaped our evolving role in the national research infrastructure ecosystem. These discussions will ensure we continue to provide world-class infrastructure, foster research excellence, and deliver impact for the health of all Australians.

In parallel with these developments, we have experienced a significant rise in the use of our services and a broadening of our user base, with more than 200 new users joining us this year – clear evidence of increasing demand and recognition within the research community.

Phenomics Australia drives researcher success, with 89% of users achieving important outcomes through our services. This momentum underscores not only the relevance of our services but also the trust and confidence our users place in us. Importantly, Phenomics Australia delivers nationally unique capabilities, with 85% of users reporting that they could not access equivalent services elsewhere in Australia.

Our team's work is strengthened by strong, consistent communication that keeps stakeholders well-informed and engaged with our strategic direction and achievements. I am also pleased to see the positive feedback from our users and the consistently high satisfaction levels we continue to receive, reflecting the value and effectiveness of our services in addressing the critical challenges faced by our local and international research communities.

I am proud to recognise our most valuable asset, our dedicated team of 85 highly skilled scientific staff, 75% of whom are women. Their exceptional expertise and commitment underpin the delivery of 42 specialised services across 20 locations and form the cornerstone of Phenomics Australia's success. It is their expertise, professionalism, and collaborative spirit that enable us to provide tailored solutions and continue to meet the diverse needs of researchers nationwide.

I look forward to building on this progress as we continue to strengthen our national capability and enable transformative research outcomes for Australia.

CEO Report

Prof. Michael Dobbie
CEO,
Phenomics Australia

Innovation is powered by the ability to answer the most demanding of questions and solve the most complex of challenges through access to the sharpest of tools, enabling exquisitely designed and expertly conducted experiments to generate the highest quality data.

I am pleased to present the Phenomics Australia 2025 Impact Report, which highlights the strategic government and institutional co-investments, major initiatives, and scientific advancements made possible through the Australian Government Department of Education's long-term support for national research infrastructure via the NCRIS program that powers Australia's R&D ecosystem.

Our 2025 report demonstrates the impact of Phenomics Australia's world-class services and deep expertise, which depends on the commitment of our partner organisations and the passion of our highly skilled workforce. From technicians and scientists to advisors, governors, executives, and policy makers, each contributes essential capability, enabled by leadership and co-investments from our nationwide alliance of partner universities, medical research institutes and state governments.

This year, we celebrate the Phenomics Australia Pipeline Accelerator Voucher Scheme, a national initiative delivered through NCRIS that has reached a significant milestone, to date supporting 57 researchers, including 33 early-career researchers, with \$2.6 million in project funding, helping bridge the gap from discovery to clinical impact and accelerating Australia's translational medical research.

In 2025, we strengthened our engagement with the research community to develop a user-centred digital strategy focused on improving the management of experimental genomics and phenomics data. Our evolving digital platforms are streamlining access to high-quality, well-curated datasets and supporting researchers and clinicians in exploring genetic links to disease. These assets form the foundation of the Phenomics Australia digital

strategy, guiding future infrastructure needs and enabling key initiatives such as biobanking and AI.

We launched the Phenomics Model Discovery Project, a national collaborative initiative between Phenomics Australia and the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), created to make it easier for researchers to locate and use data generated by pre-clinical models across health and biomedical research.

Significantly, the NCRIS Health Group, led by Phenomics Australia, partnered with the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) to deliver a timely national report describing the benefits of nationally coordinated biobanks and cohort studies in Australia and setting out how they can be achieved. Phenomics Australia is committed to supporting biobanks as essential research infrastructure and recognises that accelerated lifesaving research is dependent on nationally optimised biospecimen and data discovery and use.

In September, Phenomics Australia actively shaped discussions in the Australian and European Health Research Infrastructure Symposium in Prato, Italy. This annual international forum with our European counterparts is strengthening collaboration between European and Australian research infrastructures, including NCRIS partners. The 2025 event brought together health-focused infrastructure leaders to explore shared priorities, identify opportunities for joint initiatives, and address emerging trends and challenges across the global research infrastructure landscape.

Excellence, partnership, and a shared commitment to discovery and translation continue to inform our mission. I invite you to dive into this 2025 Phenomics Australia Impact Report to learn how we are accelerating research today. In 2026, we will continue to fuel R&D, celebrate 20 impactful years, and envision the 3rd decade of a national research infrastructure ecosystem that powers Australia's future.

About Phenomics Australia

Our Vision

Better health through the discovery of gene function.

Our Mission

Providing world-class infrastructure and expertise, collaborating for research excellence, and advocating and partnering for impact, Phenomics Australia will drive the discovery of the molecular basis of disease to benefit the health of all Australians.

Our Aspiration

Building and delivering world-class infrastructure and expertise

We will deliver cutting-edge, versatile, and sustainable phenomics infrastructure to accelerate discovery and translation.

Collaborating for research excellence

We will partner to deliver innovative research outcomes; to advance our understanding of health and disease and to inform next-generation healthcare and clinical practice.

Advocating and partnering for impact

We will reaffirm Phenomics Australia as a thought leader and influencer within the research and policy landscape.

Phenomics Australia provides academia and industry with genome-engineered cell, tissue and animal pre-clinical models necessary to study disease, underpinning what is widely known as Precision Medicine. Our experts help researchers study their models and manage their research projects to accelerate discovery and understanding of gene function, find genetic causes of diseases, develop new therapeutics and create better health treatments.

Top left: Monash Organoid Program
Top right: Stem Cell workshop
Bottom left: Science Strategy Review
Centre: Drosophila team

Our Service Locations

Our Partners

Phenomics Australia is supported by the Australian Government through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy, NCRIS. NCRIS supports Australia's research capability by investing in research infrastructure and making it accessible to researchers across the nation.

By the Numbers 2025

 1000+
Projects

 38+
Research
services

 85+
Technical
experts

 200+
New users

 186
User affiliations

 30
Different fields
of research

 \$31m
Asset valuation

 \$105m
Research grants supported

69% Female
staff

“Phenomics Australia users keep returning for more”

89% of our users are return customers.

“Ensuring continued growth and innovation in the research sector”

85% of users could not access equivalent services elsewhere in Australia.

100% Of users would recommend our facilities

“Phenomics Australia drives researcher success”

89% of users have achieved important outcomes through our services.

“Playing a crucial role in advancing research capabilities”

100% of our users report that Phenomics Australia’s expertise has played an important role in their work.

Bottom left: RIC morning tea
 Top right: CSIRO Futures Report
 Bottom right: NCRIS Health Cycle

Our Collaborations

Infrastructure Partnerships

Australian Psychiatric Research Knowledge Bank
 Phenomics Australia and Bioplatforms Australia support a national initiative to develop the Australian Psychiatric Research Knowledge Bank, advancing understanding of mental disorder causality and treatment through large-scale omics data generation and high-throughput phenomics.

NCRIS Health Group
 Through the NCRIS Health Group, Phenomics Australia supports cross-disciplinary research addressing complex health challenges, including disease modelling, drug target identification, medical product development and clinical trials.

Pipeline Accelerator Voucher Scheme
 Phenomics Australia partners with Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA), Bioplatforms Australia and the National Deuteration Facility (NDF, ANSTO) to deliver the Pipeline Accelerator scheme, collectively offering academic researchers and SMEs access to a diverse range of integrated translational medical research capabilities.

NCRIS Synthetic Biology Voucher Scheme
 Phenomics Australia partners with Bioplatforms Australia, and multiple providers across the NCRIS system, to deliver the NCRIS Synthetic Biology Voucher Scheme, collectively offering seamless access to synthetic biology capabilities and delivering sovereign value for the Australian agricultural, industrial fermentation and biomedical sectors.

Alliances

AusBiotech
 Phenomics Australia and fellow NCRIS members engage with AusBiotech to connect life sciences researchers, industry and investors, fostering collaboration and innovation.

SMART CRC (Solutions for Manufacturing Advanced Regenerative Therapies Cooperative Research Centre)
 Phenomics Australia joins forces with SMART CRC in a landmark \$238 million initiative aimed at revolutionising Regenerative Therapy by overcoming key barriers in manufacturing and access.

reNEW (Novo Nordisk Foundation Center for Stem Cell Medicine)
 In its annual report, reNEW showcased its remarkable achievements, including its partnership with Phenomics Australia and Therapeutic Innovation Australia, recognising the collaboration's contribution to stem cell medicine and regenerative research.

CSIRO (Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation)
 In collaboration with the NCRIS Health Group, Phenomics Australia contributed to the CSIRO Futures report, highlighting the benefits of nationally coordinated biobanks and cohort studies in Australia.

PURA Foundation Australia
 Phenomics Australia works with PURA Foundation Australia to support pioneering research into disease models for individuals diagnosed with PURA Syndrome, a rare neurodevelopmental disorder.

Research and Academic

Heart Disease

CAD Frontiers (Coronary Artery Disease Frontiers)

Phenomics Australia partners with CAD Frontiers to tackle coronary artery disease — the leading cause of cardiovascular death worldwide. By supporting cutting-edge research into the prevention and treatment of heart attacks, we help accelerate discoveries that directly improve patient survival and long-term heart health.

Cancer Research & Precision Oncology

CONCERT (Centre for Oncology Education Research Translation)

Through our collaboration with CONCERT and the CONCERT Biobank at the Ingham Institute, Phenomics Australia enables research that advances the prevention, detection and treatment of cancer. Access to high-quality biological samples and integrated research infrastructure supports breakthroughs in personalised cancer care.

Functional Genomics

Australian Functional Genomics Network (AFGN)

As the national infrastructure partner for the AFGN, Phenomics Australia provides researchers with advanced platforms to explore gene function and disease mechanisms. This collaboration strengthens Australia's capacity to translate genomic discoveries into clinical and biomedical impact.

Melanoma Detection & Diagnosis

Melanoma Institute Australia and ACEMID (ACRF Australian Centre of Excellence in Melanoma Imaging and Diagnosis)

Working with ACEMID and the Melanoma Institute Australia, Phenomics Australia supports earlier and more accurate melanoma diagnosis. Our secure SlideCenter platform enables digital storage and remote access to high-resolution histology images, improving collaboration among pathologists and enhancing diagnostic precision.

Top left: Melanoma in situ

Top right: STA visit

Bottom left: 2025 Australian and European Health Research Infrastructure Symposium

Bottom right: Research Infrastructure Connected

International Partnerships

IMPC (International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium) and INFRAFRONTIER

Phenomics Australia contributes to global biomedical research by supporting in vivo disease models and databases through collaboration with IMPC and the European Research Infrastructure for Modelling Human Diseases (INFRAFRONTIER), helping build a comprehensive catalogue of mammalian gene function.

ARRIGE (Association for Responsible Research and Innovation in Genome Editing)

As a member of ARRIGE, Phenomics Australia supports global governance of genome editing by promoting responsible research practices and providing infrastructure within safe and socially accepted frameworks.

Australian and European Health Research Infrastructure Symposium

Phenomics Australia supports this symposium, strengthening collaboration between Australian and European health research infrastructures with NCRIS members, and identifying and enabling joint initiatives in shared priority areas.

BBMRI-ERIC (Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium)

Phenomics Australia collaborates with BBMRI-ERIC to develop innovative technologies and processes that enable responsible access to high-quality biological samples, data and biomolecular resources.

Engagement

NCRIS Communications Network

Phenomics Australia works closely with the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) communications community to develop outreach strategies and increase awareness of Australia's national research infrastructure.

Research Infrastructure Connected (RIC)

Phenomics Australia collaborates with RIC to connect researchers and innovators with NCRIS-supported national research infrastructure, improving visibility and access across the research ecosystem.

National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS)

Phenomics Australia hosted a delegation of NCRIS members at ANU's College of Science and Medicine, showcasing its facilities, activities and commitment to fostering collaborative engagement across the NCRIS network.

Australasian Biospecimen Network Association (ABNA)

As an ABNA member, Phenomics Australia contributes to the development of a national biobanking research infrastructure investment. As part of this effort, at the ABNA conference, experts from the Australian Phenome Bank (APB) presented an integrated database solution for biospecimen tracking and data management.

Government and Policy

Australian Government

Phenomics Australia continues to engage with federal parliamentarians to inform and educate on research infrastructure capabilities and advancements, including participation in Science Meets Parliament 2025, where Phenomics Australia members met with Dr Gordon Reid MP and the Hon. Paul Fletcher MP.

NSW Government

Phenomics Australia supports strategy development and investment planning aligned with the 2021 National Research Infrastructure (NRI) Roadmap through funding from the NCRIS Support Program, ensuring equitable access to research infrastructure.

WA Government

Phenomics Australia is included in a \$47 million Western Australian investment to elevate medical research. The Harry Perkins Institute of Medical Research received \$568,500 toward a \$2 million investment in the Phenomics Australia Perkins In Vitro Node, enhancing advanced organoid production to better represent patient tumours.

Science and Technology Australia (STA)

Phenomics Australia is a member of Science and Technology Australia (STA), the national peak body that brings expertise and evidence to public policy-making, advancing the public good through supported programs and policy advice on issues affecting the STEM sector.

Supported Programs

Australian Research Council (ARC)
 Medical Research Future Fund (MRFF)
 National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC)
 Alzheimer's Association
 Australian Centre for Targeted Therapeutics (ACTT)
 Australian Functional Genomics Network (AFGN)
 Australian National Heart Foundation
 Cabrini Foundation
 Cancer Australia
 Cancer Council NSW
 Cancer Council WA
 Captain Courageous Foundation
 Care Cure Support Ltd
 Channel 7 Children's Research Foundation
 Children's Cancer Institute
 Dementia Australia Research Foundation
 European Union Horizon 2020
 Hudson Institute of Medical Research
 International Precision Child Health Partnership
 Leiden University Medical Centre
 Leukemia Foundation of Australia
 Menzies Institute for Medical Research
 MND Australia
 mRNA Victoria Research Acceleration Fund
 National Breast Cancer Foundation
 National Institutes of Health (USA)
 Neil & Norma Hill Foundation
 reNEW
 Ovarian Cancer Research Foundation
 Phenogenomics Translation Initiative
 Predator Free NZ
 PURA Foundation Australia
 Royal Society Catalyst
 Sanfilippo Children's Fund
 The Baker Heart and Diabetes Institute
 The CASS Foundation
 The Kids Research Institute Australia
 The Royal Children's Hospital Foundation
 The University of Sydney Neurodrug 2024 Scheme
 Trish Multiple Sclerosis Research Foundation
 UK Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council
 US Department of Defense
 Victorian Cancer Agency

2025

Mammalian Genome commentary published

Phenomics Australia strengthened the case for national research infrastructure by highlighting how world-class facilities drive health and medical research outcomes.

International Day of Women and Girls in Science

Phenomics Australia celebrated by showcasing the women driving our impact, championing equity and representation in science.

STA Science Meets Parliament

Phenomics Australia connected experts with federal policymakers, strengthening the link between research infrastructure and national decision-making to enhance the visibility and understanding of STEM.

NHMR Ideas Grant awarded to A/Prof. Louise Cheng

Phenomics Australia Scientific Director, A/Prof Louise Cheng secured competitive funding to advance early cancer biomarker discovery, leveraging Phenomics Australia's transgenic and disease modelling capability.

International Women's Day celebrated

Phenomics Australia recognised and amplified women's leadership and expertise across our network.

Video interview series launched

Phenomics Australia joined forces with the Department of Education to showcase national capability through interviews with our brilliant researchers, staff and technicians, highlighting Phenomics Australia's services and expertise.

SMART CRC partnership established

Phenomics Australia joined the landmark Cooperative Research Centre accelerating regenerative therapies by linking research, industry and advanced manufacturing capability, to reduce the gaps in Australia's healthcare.

Mammalian Genome commentary

Phenomics Australia published a paper exploring the complementarity and integration of animal and emerging preclinical research models and the growing role of non-animal technologies shaping future biomedical research.

Science Strategy Review

Phenomics Australia convened leadership to define future priorities and strengthen Phenomics Australia's national impact.

Unified NCRIS response to Strategic Examination of R&D

Phenomics Australia contributed to sector-wide advocacy reinforcing the importance of sustained infrastructure investment.

Pipeline Accelerator recipients announced

In partnership with TIA, BPA and NDF, a total of 40 projects to share \$1,324,362 in voucher awards were announced, granting access to national research infrastructure (NRI) to fast-track the translation of therapeutics for improving human health.

Phenomics Australia Podcast launched (Episode 4)

Phenomics Australia continued sharing expertise and innovation stories with the broader research community.

JAN

National and international conference engagement

Phenomics Australia committed to key events across the year, leading sector conferences, strengthening visibility, partnerships and collaboration opportunities.

FEB

NCRIS Forum engagement

Phenomics Australia engaged with the Department of Education and infrastructure partners to address shared challenges and collaboration across research in Australia.

MAR

APR

National Biobanking White Paper

Phenomics Australia contributed to a nationally coordinated strategy to strengthen Australia's biobanking infrastructure in partnership with sector leaders and international collaborators.

MAY

Pluripotent Stem Cell Culture workshop

Phenomics Australia delivered hands-on training for students through the iPSC Derivation and Gene Editing Facility, building national technical capability in stem cell research.

NEW! EPISODE 4

With Special Guest
Dr Lachlan Jolly

Head of the Neurobiology
Research Group
@University of Adelaide

STREAM OR
DOWNLOAD IT NOW!

JUN

2025

NCRIS Synthetic Biology Voucher Scheme launched

Phenomics Australia supported national access to synthetic biology capability through collaboration with infrastructure partners.

National Science Week 2025

Phenomics Australia celebrated the role of science and innovation alongside NCRIS and government partners.

Australian and European Health Research Infrastructure Symposium

Phenomics Australia joined leading EU and Australian health-focused research infrastructure organisations to strengthen international coordination and collaboration, and tackle shared challenges in health and life sciences.

New leadership and data capability appointments

Phenomics Australia strengthened governance, scientific leadership and data operations through new appointments across Phenomics Australia, expanding our national capability to address national research challenges.

CSIRO-supported national coordination report

Phenomics Australia contributed to evidence highlighting the value of nationally coordinated biobanks and cohort studies to enhancing Australia's capability in medical product development.

100th transgenic line milestone achieved

The Phenomics Australia Australian Drosophila Transgenic Facility completed its 100th line, expanding global research resources for genetic and disease modelling.

RIC Morning Tea

Phenomics Australia strengthened cross-Infrastructure collaboration through facility tours and sector engagement in Canberra.

STA Tour of Phenomics Australia

Phenomics Australia showcased our infrastructure capability strengthening sector understanding and advocacy.

JUL

AUG

SEP

OCT

NOV

DEC

Phenomics Model Discovery Project with ARDC

Phenomics Australia partnered with ARDC to launch a national initiative to improve discoverability and reuse of model data in health and biomedical research, removing barriers and enabling faster breakthroughs in understanding and treating disease.

AI-Enhanced Drug Discovery (AIEDD) CRC

Phenomics Australia led discussions towards a proposal for an AIEDD CRC, highlighting our commitment to supporting cutting-edge research and collaboration across the national biomedical landscape.

National conference presence

Phenomics Australia showcased our capabilities across key research meetings spanning transgenics, stem cells, organoids and high-throughput technologies, celebrating the innovation, collaboration, and excellence of national research infrastructure.

Upskilling workforce

Phenomics Australia delivered a 10-day work placement through the Histopathology and Slide Scanning Service, providing practical laboratory training and real-world experience in digital pathology to build Australia's future biomedical workforce.

Pipeline Accelerator recipients announced

In partnership with TIA, BPA and NDF, a total of 38 projects to share a total of \$1,245,261 in voucher awards were announced, with a total cash co-investment fund of \$1,495,763, facilitating access to NRI to accelerate therapeutic translation and improve human health.

Our Services

Left: Ms Veronika Purchase, Phenomics Australia Histopathology and Slide Scanning Service

Top right: The Victor Chang Innovation Centre Stem Cell Production Facility team

Our Impact

Australia's National Infrastructure for Non-Animal Modelling

Non-animal modelling (also known as New Approach Methodologies) is transforming how biomedical research is conducted in Australia. They are being increasingly used as readily accessible model types in medical product development, to determine the genomic basis of health and disease, and to complement more traditional in vivo modelling technologies.

In 2021, Phenomics Australia established the country's first nationally coordinated infrastructure for non-animal modelling, integrating leading capabilities in genome-engineered stem cells and advanced 3D organoid systems. This infrastructure, delivered through **a consortium of 13 service nodes** has filled a major national gap, giving researchers reliable access to sophisticated model systems that accelerate discovery while reducing reliance on animal models. Ensuring continued growth and innovation in the research sector with 89% of users unable to access equivalent services elsewhere in Australia.

To date, this service has delivered well over **1000 projects** for over **300 researchers**, and we are excited that an expanded total infrastructure budget of **\$12.2m to 2028** will ensure this crucial new infrastructure capability will continue to grow to meet researcher needs.

“Phenomics Australia has been excellent in supporting research infrastructure and enabling technologies. We could not do our research without this support”

Phenomics Australia user

Ensuring continued growth and innovation in the research sector

89% of users could not access equivalent services elsewhere in Australia.

Biobanking

Updates from the Australian Phenome Bank: connecting data and discovery

At the Australian Phenome Bank (APB), innovation in research support extends far beyond the laboratory bench. Over the past year, the APB has expanded its presence across the research community, sharing expertise, showcasing tools, and building stronger connections with scientists across Australia and New Zealand.

At the ABNA Conference, the APB experts presented their integrated database solution for sample tracking and data management, demonstrating how the system captures every piece of data produced by the laboratory team. By linking mouse IDs with unique barcodes seamlessly integrated into the inventory system, the APB has created a powerful resource that ensures accuracy, efficiency, and traceability for researchers nationwide.

At the ANZLAA Conference, the team welcomed attendees at their booth, promoting services and strengthening partnerships. The APB also introduced their newly implemented techniques at the OTART Conference, reflecting its commitment to continuous improvement and cutting-edge research support.

Through these initiatives, the APB continues to play a pivotal role in advancing biomedical research, ensuring that every sample tells a story and every dataset finds its place in the bigger picture of discovery.

The Phenomics Model Discovery

The Phenomics Model Discovery is a national initiative launched by Phenomics Australia and the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) to make it easier for researchers to find and use model data in health and biomedical research.

Preclinical research often relies on specialised models such as cell lines or genetically modified organisms that help scientists investigate disease mechanisms and develop new therapies. However, researchers frequently face challenges locating the right model and data, with information scattered across multiple repositories and described in inconsistent ways.

The Phenomics Model Discovery Project will address these challenges by:

- assessing the current state of FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data maturity and Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) usage in two key repositories, the Australian Phenome Bank and the Australian Stem Cell Registry
- developing a harmonised metadata and PID framework to improve data consistency and interoperability
- piloting selected improvements, including a prototype discovery portal, to demonstrate how harmonised data can support better search, access, and reuse
- creating a plan for scaling these approaches to other Phenomics Australia resources in the future.

In Vivo Genome Engineering & Disease Modelling

Key milestone hit in exploring new treatments for epilepsy

The Challenge:

Developmental and epileptic encephalopathies (DEE) are a group of severe neurodevelopmental disorders that cause children from infancy to suffer seizures, often accompanied by developmental delay, behavioural and cognitive deficits. Affecting 1 in every 600 children, there is no one specific cause for DEEs, making identifying the underlying cause for these debilitating childhood epilepsies difficult to treat. Current treatments focus on managing seizures, but they offer little benefit for the broader developmental challenges faced by affected children.

The Solution:

To better understand the condition and accelerate the search for effective treatments, a team from the Florey Institute incorporated a variation found in KCNQ2 gene from a Melbourne child with DEE into a mouse model developed with support from the Monash Genome Modification Platform, allowing the mice to mimic the human disease. One of the most frequently identified causes of DEE is variations in the KCNQ2 gene, and the results of this study suggest that the KCNQ2 gene plays a role in early brain development, not just seizures.

The Future:

These results open new avenues for the development of treatments for KCNQ2 DEE that could benefit patients beyond seizure control. Mouse models, such as these, are essential; not only do they help us uncover the mechanisms of the disease, but they also provide a platform to screen existing and novel therapies that could improve the lives of patients.

"By bridging the gap between genetic discovery and treatment development, this new disease model represents a significant step toward personalised therapies for children affected by KCNQ2 DEE," Associate Professor Snezana Maljevic said.

There is MAGEC driving discovery with advanced disease models

The Challenge:

Modelling human disease is challenging due to the complexity of human conditions, where genetic, molecular, and environmental factors interact in dynamic ways. Capturing the full spectrum of disease progression is difficult, often leading to poor translation of findings into clinical success.

The Solution:

Sophisticated pre-clinical models provide critical translational value by replicating key molecular, physiological, and pathological features of human disease. The Melbourne Advanced Gene Editing Centre (MAGEC) – a Phenomics Australia node based at the Olivia Newton-John Cancer Research Institute (ONJCRI) – is a leading facility specialising in advanced CRISPR gene-editing technologies to generate pre-clinical models.

Through the development of novel mouse models, MAGEC has helped those with microcephaly, an incurable birth defect, and provided a deeper understanding of the disease to researchers. The node has also helped advance the understanding of tumour-prevention mechanisms in blood cancer, enabling new avenues for treatment. These models have also strengthened cancer drug development and paved the way for safer, more targeted cancer therapies overall, through target protein studies. MAGEC has supported the first-established novel next-generation gene-editing tool for modelling and interrogating human disease, advancing gene editing capabilities for cancer and medical research through unprecedented genetic manipulation.

The Future:

By strengthening understanding of disease mechanisms and therapeutic strategies, these models are a powerful tool. Pre-clinical animal models will allow therapies to be tailored with greater accuracy, improving the prediction of patient-specific responses and accelerating safer, more effective treatments for better patient outcomes. Ultimately, enabling better health outcomes for Australians.

In Vitro Genome Engineering & Disease Modelling

3D-printed organs? It's not as far-fetched as you think

The Challenge:

In 2015, Professor Adam Perriman was experimenting with hacked plastic 3D printers at the University of Bristol, searching for a way to print living biological materials. The goal was bold: to create animal-free models for better studying diseases and, one day, even print entire organs.

The Solution:

Now at the Australian National University (ANU) and supported by Phenomics Australia's in vitro genome engineering and disease modelling node, the ANU Centre for Therapeutic Discovery (ACTD), Professor Perriman and his team are pioneering bioprinting, using specialised bioinks to print living cells that grow into tissue and replicate different types of cancer cells for medical research. Bioprinting offers a perfect solution to mass-produce cancer models to be tested against a variety of treatment options. This technique can also be used for developing personalised medical treatment regimens for an individual diagnosed with cancer.

The Future:

While printing entire organs remains a challenge, ANU researchers are steadily moving from small tissue structures toward this transformative goal. Associate Professor Ameer George, Head of the ACTD, explains, "3D bioprinting is revolutionising therapeutic development by producing miniaturised, lifelike human tissue models that accelerate the discovery of more effective therapies. As the technology advances, it promises personalised medicine and a new era of faster, better treatments."

Basics in Pluripotent Stem Cell Culture, a successful workshop

The Pluripotent Stem Cell Culture Workshop, hosted by the Phenomics Australia iPSC Derivation and Gene Editing Facility, ran from 6–8 May at Murdoch Children's Research Institute.

Over three afternoons, 17 participants gained hands-on experience in essential cell culture techniques for working with human pluripotent stem cells, including passaging, freeze/thawing, removing differentiated cells, and managing challenging cell lines.

Attendees came from institutions such as MCRI, UNSW, CSIRO, the University of Melbourne, Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, and RMIT. The workshop received excellent feedback, with participants praising the supportive environment, practical structure, and valuable skills gained.

"This workshop is truly awesome and one of a kind! I really appreciate all the hard work put in by the organising team to make it such a successful event. Their efforts have made a real difference!"

"I think the workshop was a very good opportunity and I have learned a lot during those three days which I will certainly apply to my own work and share with colleagues. Thanks a lot!"

Left: MAGEC team members

Top centre: Associate Professor Snezana Maljevic. Image credit The Florey.

Bottom centre: Pluripotent Stem Cell Culture Workshop participants

Top centre: COVID research
Bottom centre: Monash Functional Genomics Platform team

Functional Genomics & High-Throughput Screening

Exploring therapeutic targets against SARS-CoV-2 and the host factors influencing COVID pathogenesis

The Challenge:

Understanding how SARS-CoV-2 interacts with human cells is key to finding new treatments for COVID-19. But identifying the host factors that drive infection and disease progression is highly complex and requires specialised facilities, expertise, and collaboration.

The Solution:

CSIRO's Host Response team at the Australian Centre for Disease Preparedness (ACDP), together with the Phenomics Australia node, the Victorian Centre for Functional Genomics (VCFG) at Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre, developed a genome-wide screening assay targeting host-encoded microRNAs (miRNAs). By systematically knocking down the entire miRNA genome, the team identified factors that either promote or inhibit SARS-CoV-2 replication. Transfection, cell biology steps and high-content imaging were performed at VCFG, while viral infection studies were conducted under BSL-44 conditions at CSIRO ACDP. The full dataset and findings have been openly shared through Scientific DATA, providing a valuable global research resource.

The Future:

This study not only advances the search for therapeutic targets against SARS-CoV-2 but also establishes a framework for tackling other emerging infectious diseases. By continuing to combine high-content functional genomics with world-class biosecurity facilities, researchers are paving the way for faster therapeutic discovery and stronger pandemic preparedness.

Hidden clues in junk DNA unlock new insights into Alzheimer's disease

The Challenge:

Alzheimer's disease is a complex and devastating neurodegenerative condition, affecting millions worldwide and placing a growing burden on families and healthcare systems. While many studies have focused on protein-coding genes, much of the human genome, often dismissed as "Junk DNA", remains poorly understood. This has limited our ability to uncover the early molecular drivers of Alzheimer's and develop effective disease-modifying treatments.

The Solution:

Using CRIP-seq, a new high-throughput strategy that measures gene expression changes across hundreds of genetic perturbations, researchers generated a pooled sgRNA library targeting non-coding genetic elements implicated in Alzheimer's disease. With support from the Phenomics Australia node, the Monash Functional Genomics Platform, UNSW scientists screened nearly 1,000 potential DNA "switches," known as enhancers, identifying more than 150 regulatory interactions. The study revealed enhancers that regulate key brain cells that support neurons, astrocytes, as well as genes linked to Alzheimer's risk.

The Future:

By targeting regulatory elements in specific cell types, scientists aim to modulate disease-relevant genes in astrocytes without affecting neurons or other brain cells. This precision opens new opportunities for safer, more controlled and more effective therapeutic strategies for Alzheimer's disease.

Pathology

Updates from the Pathology team: A new level of precision, speed, and reliability for haematology analysis

Following our ongoing commitment to excellence in research, the Phenomics Australia Histopathology & Slide Scanning Service has added the Sysmex XNI000-V haematology analyser to the service. This system delivers a highly comprehensive complete blood count (CBC) and differential blood analysis, and it is now available to all researchers.

As part of the comprehensive mouse necropsy evaluation, a CBC and blood differential test is performed on terminal blood. This provides a general health status of the animal at end stage and other indicators that align with and support associated histopathology results.

Specifically tailored for veterinary applications, the XNI000-V is validated for mice and rats, and a number of other commonly tested animal species, bringing a new level of precision, speed, and reliability to our service. Our staff are always available to assist, and sample results are generated in minutes. We can't wait to show you what this technology can do!

Top right: Ms Tina Cardamone, Phenomics Australia Histopathology and Slide Scanning service

Advancing early Melanoma detection: Phenomics Australia & ACEMID collaboration

The Challenge:

Every year, more than 18,000 Australians are diagnosed with melanoma. According to Australian Centre of Excellence in Melanoma Imaging & Diagnosis (ACEMID) Project Leader Prof. H. Peter Soyer (The University of Queensland), identifying early changes in skin across such a large population is a monumental challenge, but it is achievable.

"In the near future, we hope to see targeted melanoma screening join the ranks of Australia's other national health screening programs, informed by the latest research data", Prof. Soyer said.

The Solution:

Phenomics Australia's Histopathology & Slide Scanning Node is working with the ACEMID Pathology team to drive new advances in the early detection and diagnosis of melanoma, scanning and securely storing digital histology slides of skin biopsies from ACEMID in our secure online platform, SlideCenter. This system allows pathologists to remotely view and interrogate high-resolution histological images.

The Future:

"We are excited to continue supporting ACEMID with high-throughput slide scanning and secure digital access, ensuring their pathologists and researchers have the tools they need to advance Australia's fight against melanoma." Ms Tina Cardamone, service manager of Phenomics Australia Histopathology and Digital Slide node said.

The Pipeline Accelerator Voucher Scheme

Through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS), a powerful collaboration between Phenomics Australia, Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA), ANSTO's National Deuteration Facility (NDF), and Bioplatforms Australia is supporting Australia's translational medical research landscape like never before.

This unified national effort directly addresses the medical products challenge outlined in the **2021 National Research Infrastructure (NRI) Roadmap**, providing researchers and innovators with the tools and support needed to move discoveries **from the lab to real-world impact**.

To foster greater engagement with Australia's world-class research infrastructure, the **Pipeline Accelerator Voucher Scheme** offers **financial support to academic researchers and small-to-medium enterprises (SMEs)**. This initiative helps bridge the gap between early-stage research and clinical application by facilitating access to a wide range of translational capabilities—from understanding the molecular basis of disease to conducting clinical trials.

Early and Mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) and **female researchers** are strongly encouraged to apply as lead applicants, supporting greater diversity and opportunity across the research landscape.

2

Rounds per year

57

Voucher recipients

2023

Phenomics Australia partnered with Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA) on the Pipeline Accelerator voucher scheme on April 2023

2024

Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation (ANSTO)'s National Deuteration Facility (NDF) joined the scheme for the 2024 rounds

2025

Bioplatforms Australia joined the scheme for the 2025 rounds

33

EMCRs

\$2.6M

Project support

Case study - Paediatric brain disorder

The TRAPPC4 disorder is a rare paediatric neurological condition causing early-onset seizures, neurodevelopmental delay and brain atrophy in affected children. There are no treatments for this devastating disorder. The findings of this project led by **Dr Nicole Van Bergen**, Team Leader with the Murdoch Children's Research Institute (MCRI) Brain and Mitochondrial group, is the first step in discovering new treatments for this childhood brain disorder. By creating models of the genetic disease, researchers will be able to accurately study the disorder, how the disease mechanisms work and identify possible treatments.

"The voucher has been a pivotal support of my research on a rare neurodevelopmental disorder. We are very excited to be using these cell lines to generate organoids and neurons for our screening program."

Dr Nicole Van Bergen.

This breakthrough was supported by the Phenomics Australia Pipeline Accelerator 2023-24 Round 1 scheme and the Phenomics Australia iPSC Derivation & Gene Editing Facility Node at MCRI, a node specialised in *in vitro* genome editing and disease modelling.

Case study - Lab-grown 'tiny hearts'

Genetic heart disease and inherited heart conditions like cardiomyopathies, are incredibly difficult to understand and treat due to our limitations in disease modelling. A collaboration between QIMR Berghofer, Murdoch Children's Research Institute (MCRI) and the Royal Children's Hospital has developed lab-grown 'tiny hearts'. These 'tiny hearts' created by QIMR Berghofer's **Prof. James Hudson** and fellow scientists mimic human heart muscle and behave like a genuine adult heart. These findings will greatly accelerate the way treatments are identified and tested for heart related disease.

"The support of the Voucher scheme enabled us to generate a novel line, which enabled us to perform lineage tracing of stromal cells in human cardiac organoids for the first time. This provided really important information to show that these cells resemble native cardiac cells. We hope to now extend these findings and discover new therapeutics targeting the stromal cells for heart failure."

Prof. James Hudson.

This project was supported by the Phenomics Australia Pipeline Accelerator 2022-23 Round 2 scheme and the Phenomics Australia iPSC Derivation & Gene Editing Facility Node at MCRI, a node specialised in *in vitro* genome editing and disease modelling.

Case study - Oral Cancer Organoid Biobank

Oral squamous cell carcinoma is a devastating disease with a poor prognosis, due to late diagnosis, limited treatment efficacy, and the resistance to current therapies. The project, led by **Dr Rikki Brown**, Research Associate in the Laboratory for Cancer Medicine at the Harry Perkins Institute of Medical Research, has been crucial in improving Australia's capability to evaluate novel therapeutics. Together with the Phenomics Australia's Translational Cancer Research Program Node, the team has begun establishing the foundations for a sustainable biobank of oral cancer organoids at the Perkins Cancer Biobank in Western Australia, offering invaluable models for genomic analysis and therapeutic testing.

"This project has laid the essential groundwork for building a biobank of oral cancer organoids—an invaluable resource developed by Western Australian researchers. By establishing clinically relevant models that more accurately reflect the disease, we are creating a foundation for more successful drug discovery and future therapeutic innovations."

Dr Rikki Brown.

This initiative was supported by the Phenomics Australia Pipeline Accelerator 2023-24 Round 1 scheme and the Phenomics Australia Translational Cancer Research Program Node, a node specialised in *in vitro* genome editing and disease modelling and biobanking.

Our Team

Phenomics Australia Board

The Phenomics Australia Board provides oversight and strategic guidance for all Phenomics Australia activities and investments. The Board members provide extensive experience in scientific strategy, biomedical research, policy, governance, industry engagement and commercialisation.

Dr Liz Jazwinska - Chair
Dr Carol Wicking - Science Advisor
Dr Fabio Turatti (from December 2024)
Prof. Tim Senden
Prof. Graham Mann (until Q1 2025)
Dr Michael Poidinger
Prof. Glenn Withers

Phenomics Australia Scientific Directors

The Phenomics Australia Scientific Leaders are responsible for the delivery of Phenomics Australia's various services, while regularly providing highly informed scientific, technical, and strategic advice to the Board.

Prof. Kaylene Simpson
 Head of the Victorian Centre For Functional Genomics (VCFG) - Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre

Dr Andrew Kueh
 Head of the Melbourne Advanced Genome Editing Centre (MAGEC) - Olivia Newton-John Cancer Research Institute

Prof. Paul Thomas
 Head of the South Australian Genome Editing (SAGE) Facility - South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute (SAHMRI)

Dr Alexander Combes
 Head of the Monash Genome Modification Platform (MGMP) - Monash University

Prof. Janet Keast
 Head of the Phenomics Australia Histopathology and Slide Scanning Service - University of Melbourne

Dr Louise Winteringham
 Head of the Translational Cancer Research Program - Harry Perkins Institute of Medical Research

A/Prof. Ameer George
 Head of the ANU Centre for Therapeutic Discovery (ACTD) - Australian National University

Dr Thierry Jarde
 Director of the Monash Organoid Program - Monash University

Dr Sara Howden
 Head of the Induced Pluripotent Stem Cell (iPSC) Derivation & Gene Editing Facility - Murdoch Children's Research Institute

Prof. Christine Wells
 Chair of Stem Cell Systems - University of Melbourne

Prof. Ruth Arkell
 John Curtin School of Medical Research (JCSMR) Associate Director, Research Infrastructure - Australian National University

Prof. Alice Pébay
 Head of the Stem Cell Disease Modelling Laboratory - University of Melbourne

Dr Andrew Prowse
 Head of the UQ In-Vitro Genome Engineering and Disease Modelling Service (IGEDMS) and the Australian Organoid Facility at the Australian Institute for Bioengineering and Nanotechnology (AIBN) - University of Queensland (UQ)

Prof. Sally Dunwoodie
 Deputy Director of the Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute

A/Prof. Sefi Rosenbluh
 Head of the Monash Functional Genomics Platform (MFGP) - Monash University

Prof. Simon Barry
 Head of the Functional Genomics South Australia (FGSA) - University of Adelaide

Prof. Kieran Harvey
 Co-Head of the Australian Transgenic Drosophila Facility - Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre

A/Prof. Louise Cheng
 Co-Head of the Australian Transgenic Drosophila Facility - Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre

Phenomics Australia Executive Team

The Executive Team is responsible for the day-to-day operation of Phenomics Australia.

Prof. Michael Dobbie
 Chief Executive Officer

A/Prof. Jim Hennessy
 Deputy CEO

Dr Marina Trigueros
 Communications Manager

Dr John Parisot
 Strategic Partnerships Advisor

Ms Sarah Dreese
 Executive Support Officer

Dr Twishi Gulati
 National Service Coordinator

Ms Sarah Nisbet
 Director, Digital Platforms

Ms Bridget Elliott-Rudder
 Communications Assistant

Mr Nick Rossow
 Data Operations Manager, Digital Platforms

Ms Minal Abassi
 Digital Analyst, Digital Platforms

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